

Effects of MoSi₂ additions on the properties of (Hf- and Zr-)B₂ composites

produced by pressureless sintering

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ABSTRACT

Composites in the HfB₂-(5-20 MoSi₂) system were produced from powder mixtures and densified through pressureless sintering at 1950°C. Microstructure and mechanical properties were compared with pressureless sintered ZrB₂-based composites containing the same amount of MoSi₂. The addition of MoSi₂ allowed the achievement of highly dense bodies without degrading the high temperature behaviour. Flexural strength measured at 1500°C in air were in the range of 480-580 MPa.

Keywords: Borides, composites, sintering, microstructure, mechanical properties

Ceramic materials based on hafnium and zirconium-diboride systems are currently considered materials of great interest for ultra-high-temperature applications because of their combination of engineering properties such as high melting points, solid state stability and good thermo-chemical and thermo-mechanical properties [1-4]. The major concern of these compounds is the densification. Due to the high melting point (>3200°C), the sintering of Hf- and Zr-borides needs pressure-assisted sintering procedures at temperatures of the order of 2000°C or even higher [2-6]. The incorporation of additives has been reported to improve the sinterability, but it is often found to be detrimental for high temperature properties [7-9].

In this contribution, MoSi₂ was selected as ceramic additive for Hf- and Zr- borides. It has already been shown that MoSi₂ is effective for the sintering of ZrB₂ either by hot pressing or by pressureless sintering [10,11]. The addition of MoSi₂ can ultimately improve the oxidation resistance of the composites, thanks to the development of a protective silica-based surface layer [12]. MoSi₂ was also proved to be effective for the densification of HfB₂ when using pressure-assisted techniques [13]. The purpose of the present work is to study the fabrication, microstructure and properties of HfB₂-(5-20 vol%) MoSi₂ composites by pressureless sintering.

The microstructure and properties of selected materials are analyzed and compared to those of ZrB₂-based composites containing the same amounts of additive.

Commercial powders were used to prepare the specimens: HfB₂ (Cerac Incorporated, Milwaukee, USA), particle size range 0.5-5 μm, impurities: Al (0.07%), Fe (0.01%), Zr (0.47%); ZrB₂ Grade B (H.C. Starck, Germany), impurities (max. content): C: 0.25 wt%, O: 2 wt%, N: 0.25 wt%, Fe: 0.1 wt%, Hf: 0.2 wt%, particle size range 0.1-8 μm; MoSi₂ (Aldrich, Milwaukee, USA), particle size range 0.5-6 μm, oxygen content 1 wt %. The compositions prepared are summarized in Table I. The powder mixtures were milled for 24 h in ethanol using zirconia milling media, subsequently dried in a rotary evaporator and sieved to -60 mesh screen size. Pellets with 1-3 cm of diameter were prepared by uniaxial pressing followed by cold isostatic pressing under 350 MPa. The pellets were pressureless sintered in a resistance-heated graphite furnace under a flowing argon atmosphere (~1 atm) at different temperatures and holding times; sintering cycles are summarized in Table I.

All the samples were examined using X-ray diffraction (Siemens D500, Germany) to identify crystalline phases. For microstructural investigations, the specimens were polished with diamond paste to 0.25 μm. The microstructures were analyzed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Cambridge S360, UK) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS, INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK).

The mechanical properties were tested on selected compositions. Vickers microhardness (HV) was measured on polished surfaces, with a load of 9.81 N, using a Zwick 3212 tester. Young's modulus (E) was measured by the resonance frequency method on 28×8×0.8 mm³ specimens using an H&P gain-phase analyzer. Fracture toughness (K_{IC}) was evaluated using the chevron-notched beam (CNB) in flexure on a Instron 6025 testing machine using specimens with dimensions 25×2×2.5 mm³. The specimens were deformed with a crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min. The "slice model" equation of Munz et al. [14] was used for the calculation of K_{IC}. Three specimens were tested for each material. On the same machine, the 4 pt flexural strength (σ), up to 1500°C in air, was measured on chamfered bars 25×2.5×2 mm³, using a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. For the high-temperature tests, a soaking time of 18 min was set to reach thermal equilibrium. Five samples were tested for each temperature point.

Pressureless sintering tests were carried out in the temperature range of 1900-1950°C for HfB₂-based materials and in the 1800-1900°C range for ZrB₂-based materials (Table I). Sintering tests were also attempted for unaddicted powders at 1950°C, leading to very poor densification. In order to achieve high density bodies,

the sintering cycle for HfB₂-based materials was set at 1950°C/60 min, irrespective of the additive content. Tests at 1900°C revealed that even with 20 vol% additive, the final density remained as low as 92%. For ZrB₂-based materials, the best sintering results were obtained at 1850°C/60 min for the composition with 20 vol% MoSi₂. It is worth noting that the sintering temperatures needed for the HfB₂-based materials to achieve densities >95% were generally 50-100°C higher than those of the ZrB₂-based materials, for the same doping level.

Microstructural characterization is presented for compositions with 5 and 20 vol% MoSi₂, namely HB5, HB20, ZB5 and ZB20.

HfB₂-based composites. HfB₂, MoSi₂ and traces of HfO₂ were the crystalline phases identified by X-ray diffraction (as displayed for the HB20 composition in Fig.1). The fracture surface of the HfB₂-MoSi₂ composites showed a transgranular fracture mode (an example is reported in Fig. 2 for the HB20 composition). In Fig. 3a-b, the polished sections of compositions HB5 and HB20 show a very regular microstructure, with little residual porosity. In agreement with density measurements, a higher level of porosity was observed for the composition with lower content of the intermetallic phase. HfB₂ grains have a rounded shape while the MoSi₂ phase has an irregular morphology with very low dihedral angles (20-30°). This peculiar characteristic indicates that MoSi₂ was very ductile at the sintering temperature and was accommodated between the voids left by the HfB₂ skeleton. This phenomenon is not surprising since the sintering temperature (1950°C) for this sample was very close to the melting point of MoSi₂ (≈2020°C) [15]. The HfB₂ mean grain size is about 1.5 μm independent of the amount of MoSi₂ (see Table I). The analysis of secondary phases by EDS confirmed the presence of HfO₂ which appears as bright contrasting particles, HfC and traces of a Mo-B phase (Fig.4). The presence of HfC may be due to carbon contamination deriving from graphite crucible and supports. The presence of HfO₂ can be due to both oxygen contamination of the starting HfB₂ powder and to oxygen take-up during the milling procedure.

ZrB₂-based composites: The microstructural features of the sample containing 20 vol% were described earlier [11,12]. However, for the sake of clarity they are briefly summarized in the following. The crystalline phases detected by X-ray diffraction were ZrB₂ and MoSi₂ [11]. The 5 vol% MoSi₂-containing sample (ZB5) showed a higher level of residual porosity compared with the 20 vol% MoSi₂-containing one (ZB20). On the polished sections (Fig. 5a-b), the rounded grains are ZrB₂ phase whilst the MoSi₂ phase is characterized by an irregular shape, similar to the HfB₂-based samples. The mean grain size of the ZrB₂ grains was about 2.5 μm, for all the compositions. Occasionally, ZrC and MoB phases were detected in the microstructure [11,12], similar to the findings of HfB₂-based composites. For this system, a partial formation of (Zr, Mo)-B solid solutions is

hypothesized, on the basis of following observations. First, ZrB_2 grains were found to have a sub-structure, resembling a core-shell structure. By EDS analysis, carried out with reduced energy in order to limit the beam lateral spread, pure ZrB_2 phase was recognized in the cores, while Zr, B and small amounts of Mo were detected in the shell (Fig.5c). Furthermore, by X-ray diffraction carried out at high diffraction angles ($2\text{-theta} > 100^\circ$), additional ZrB_2 peaks, very close to those of pure ZrB_2 hexagonal phase, but slightly shifted towards higher angles, were detected. This findings deserve a deeper investigation and are presently object of further work. However, it must be mentioned that the formation of (Zr, Mo)-B solid solutions was already reported for pressureless sintered ZrB_2 -SiC composites containing Mo as sintering additive [16].

Interestingly, neither microstructural evidence nor X-ray diffraction accounted for a similar behavior in the case of HfB_2 -based samples. The tendency of forming solid solutions could explain the higher sinterability of the ZrB_2 -composites compared to HfB_2 -composites.

Mechanical properties are summarized in Table II, for the compositions of interest. The microhardness of the composites was negatively affected by the addition of $MoSi_2$, for which a hardness of 9-11 GPa is reported [17], and by residual porosity. The expected decrease of hardness with increasing the $MoSi_2$ contents was counterbalanced by an increase of the final density, therefore hardness values were not significantly different for $MoSi_2$ doping level of 5 and 20 vol%. HfB_2 -based composites were harder (~18 GPa) than the corresponding ZrB_2 -based composites (~16 GPa), probably due to the lower mean grain size. Concerning Young's modulus, values for the tested materials were quite high (442-489 GPa, Table II), thanks to the high stiffness of the constituent phases. The highest value was found for the ZB5 sample. The values found for all the samples are comparable to those reported for monolithic hot pressed HfB_2 and ZrB_2 [1,5,6].

The measured values of fracture toughness ($3\text{-}4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) are in agreement with those reported in the literature for these materials, even if obtained with different sintering technique and sintering aids [9,13]. As transgranular fracture was observed for all the compositions, it can be concluded that the addition of $MoSi_2$ did not have any significant effect on the crack propagation behaviour of these specimens.

There are few or no reports on strength results of pressureless sintered Zr-, Hf-borides. A values of 444 ± 30 has been recently reported for a pressureless sintered ZrB_2 monolithic sample [5], which is close to the results presented in this work (HB5: 472 MPa, ZB5: 569 MPa). Despite the higher mean grain size, the ZrB_2 -based composites were generally stronger than HfB_2 -ones, at room temperature. HfB_2 -based compositions were in fact more prone to formation of voids and large $MoSi_2$ agglomerates, during the forming stage. Furthermore,

it can be observed that, at room temperature, the increase of MoSi₂ content caused a decrease of strength for both the borides. This feature was already found for HfC-MoSi₂ composites [18] and, as for that case, it was attributed to the formation of large agglomerates of the sintering phase, MoSi₂, which acted as critical defects.

The beneficial effect of MoSi₂ was disclosed at high temperature. Strength values measured at 1200°C were close to or even higher than those found at room temperature (Table II). This improvement of strength was attributed to the sealing of surface defects by means of silica glass formed during the test, as confirmed by the fractographic study of the fractured bars tested in air (not shown). At this temperature, significant formation of silica occurred as a consequence of MoSi₂ oxidation [19]. At 1500°C, the strength values were in the range of 480-580 MPa. The higher value of HB20 sample was very likely due to higher refractoriness of HfB₂ and the protective action of MoSi₂. After the test, all the sample surfaces were found to be coated by a silica layer, likewise for the materials tested at 1200°C. The load-displacement curves were linear up to fracture either at 1200 or at 1500°C, confirming the high refractoriness of the constituent phases. Finally, at high temperature, an increase of strength with increasing the MoSi₂ content was found, confirming the protective action exerted by the intermetallic phase. The high temperature strength values were comparable to or even higher than the results reported for ZrB₂- or HfB₂-based composites containing various kind of sintering aids [7-9].

From the technological point of view, the ability to sinter these materials using a conventional pressureless sintering technique offers the advantage of low-cost production of complex-shaped components with properties comparable to those of materials sintered using more expensive technologies.

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TABLE I. Composition, sintering conditions and final relative densities.

TABLE II. Mean grain size and mechanical properties of selected materials.

Fig.1. X-ray diffraction spectra of $\text{HfB}_2+20 \text{ vol\% MoSi}_2$ composite. $\text{CuK}\beta$: residual $\text{CuK}\beta$ radiation.

Fig. 2. Fracture surface of HB20.

Fig.3. Polished sections of a) HB5, b) HB20. Legend: 1= HfB_2 , 2= MoSi_2 , 3= HfO_2 .

Fig. 4. EDS analysis of secondary phases in the HB20 composition. Legend: 2= MoSi_2 , 4= HfC , 5= MoB .

Fig. 5. Typical microstructure of samples a) ZB5 and b) ZB20 c) EDS analysis of solid solution in ZB20 composition. Legend: 1= ZrB_2 , 2= MoSi_2 , ss=(Zr,Mo)B solid solution.

TABLE I. Composition, sintering conditions and final relative densities.

Label	UHTC	MoSi ₂	Sintering Conditions	Relative Density	Weight loss
		Vol%	°C, min	%	%
HB0	HfB ₂	0	1950, 60	89	0.8
HB5		5	1950, 60	97	1.4
HB10		10	1950, 60	98	1.5
HB20		20	1900, 60	92	2.0
HB20		20	1950, 60	98	2.0
ZB0	ZrB ₂	0	1950, 60	90	1.6
ZB5		5	1800, 60	86	2
ZB5		5	1850, 60	92	2.4
ZB5		5	1900, 60	96	2.4
ZB15		15	1800, 60	98	2.3
ZB20		20	1850, 60	99	2.3

TABLE II. Mean grain size and mechanical properties of selected materials.

Sample	M.g.s.	HV1.0	E	K _{IC}	σ _{RT}	σ _{1200°C}	σ _{1500°C}
	μm	GPa	GPa	MPa·m ^{1/2}	MPa	MPa	MPa
HB5	1.6	18.2±0.3	442±4	4.0±0.3	472±10	501±89	486±19
HB20	1.5	18.2±0.6	482±4	4.1±0.4	405±72	548±56	577±39
ZB5	2.6	15.2±1.0	516±4	2.9±0.1	569±54	533±87	488±46
ZB20	2.5	16.0±0.4	489±4	4.0±0.6	531±46	655±17	500±58

FIGURES

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

